

EURAKNOS

Horizon 2020

Coordination and Support Action

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INTRODUCTION

The kick off meeting of the EURAKNOS project took place in Brussels the 9th and the 10th of January 2019.

People present at the meeting the first day:

Maria-Jose A. (EC), Pieter S., Nathan D.G., Lieve H., Bjorn V., Lies H., Elena F. (UGent), Sylvia B. (Agrolink Flanders/EV ILVO), Els B., Alexander O. (PSKW), Patrick S., Maxime M. (IDELE), Lisa Williams v.D. (RAU), Spyros F., Hercules P. (AUA), Maria Rosa M.L., Nuria F.D. (USC), Elodie P., Franz J.M., (GLZ), Davino V.H., Philip V., Nikolas T., Liesbeth B. (LFG), Szabolcs V., Csaba P., Szilveszter P. (AKI), Andrew L. (IFA), Ilse A.R., Merete S. (ICROFS AU), Timea R. (NAK), Pauline B. (ACTA), Konstantin M., Pille K. (ARC), Bram M. (IFOAM EU)

Excused: Jessica S. (RAU)

FIRST DAY

MORNING

INTRODUCTION PROJECT PARTNERS

From **9.00 to 9.30** Partners and the EC project officer introduced themselves and presented their organisations:

Table 1. Introduction of the different partners in the project consortium (presentations available on the google drive and in the annex of this deliverable).

Partners	Link to presentation	Google drive
UGent	Annex 1: UGent presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=11YgNOnuHPZN9rdvOEUwRxcNXmQsYi0Bj
Agrolink		presentation merged with UGent presentation
PSKW	Annex 2: PSKW presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1eL-v E-MXHb2nOBR8XjxACM9gfGPCmz-
IDELE	Annex 3: IDELE presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1Jfk3IPbJVLt71wlw-363J2CorP_zm_2J
RAU	Annex 4: RAU presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ix7jllknXAExBPdHuNu1syQKkMfvNoNb
USC	Annex 5: USC presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1s3hs6uz1EY1Wc8EN_9EUMVKRFhCYhBO8
GLZ	Annex 6: GLZ presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1-4nvSvcbHDv0Gb2yV4R26xoy4OTarQb7oeDqnbuB36Q
AKI	Annex 7: AKI presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1xFh75t2uhkuy82BzNQ1G2zlni-2H182P

IFA	no	no presentation, just oral communication based on website https://www.innovationforagriculture.org.uk/
ICROFS AU	Annex 8: ICROFS AU presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1m3fyGYyd1y7OUoGo9YpHOFcb9bWgYiu1
NAK	no	no presentation, just oral communication
ACTA	Annex 9: ACTA presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1rG05-yK0Sh-icYk7CyGS1BszvWvXko54
ARC	Annex 10: ARC presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1MXxw-3h-fz9sIGcu7Hv7e2YbQh2ILCkZMzqHTMjYTw
IFOAM EU	Annex 11: IFOAM EU presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=15CyujRE6BBnh04C62vgv3FTyVks7SBGN
AUA	Annex 12: AUA presentation	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1GWNzQwe5d2n5JjH0uuKYIVm8IEC_cNybjnmt5NvEm_s

INTRODUCTION EC PROJECT OFFICER

From **9.30 to 10.15** Maria José Amaral, the EC project officer presented REA (Annex 13: REA presentation), H2020 framework and EURAKNOS expectations. She highlighted how TNs are part of rural renaissance call to promote innovation in agriculture to support SDGs.

The EC project officer underlined the importance of the following points:

- All the partners should report by email their activities and progresses every 3 months to the coordinator. Every year an overall well-structured report of the activities has to be made.
- The project should use impact indicators for communication and dissemination, the goal is to have a boost in impact. If this impact will not be reached, a clear motivation should be provide.
- All public deliverables (DLV) will be published on CORDIS.
- The project has to take care of communication: communication is the conversion of the obtained project results into words to be transferred to and understandable for a broad public. With the obtained results, the best strategy of communication has to be looked for.

Moreover it has been established that the acknowledgment of EU funding will have to be added only in the banner of the account page in all social media posts. Concerning the use of Twitter, it is enough to report it only on the twitter page and not on each tweet.

Additionally the EC project officer clarified that the Data Management Plan (DMP) is separate from the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

10.45-11.00 Coffee break.

START PROJECT

From **11.00 to 11.30** UGent presented the Management and Coordination team

- Pieter S. is the coordinator of EURAKNOS project, all communication with the scientific

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- officer should pass through him;
- Lies H. is in charge of solving practical issues (e.g. travel-hotel-events);
 - Nathan D.G. will take care of the internal communication tools and evaluate the deliverables (also oversee the timely delivery and quality/impact of the deliverables);
 - Sylvia B. will be in charge of networking activities (e.g. oversight SIB and KIP and related activities);
 - Bjorn VDK. and Lieve H. are responsible for all financial and administration issues related to the grant agreement.

Concerning GDPR and the DMP, it was clarified that the data manager is not the same as the data protection officer (DPO). In fact small organisations do not need a DPO.

WP5 COMMUNICATION PLAN (IfA)

From **11.30 to 13.30** Andrew Lazenby presented WP5 communication plan (Annex 14: WP5 communication plan presentation).

The goal is to keep everything simple and to convey key messages with EURAKNOS. It is important to first get the basics right. Outreach needs to be built, also on social media and input from each partner are needed.

The following points were discussed:

- To launch the website: each partner has to provide logo, background info, contact details etc. This information must be sent by the end of the week (13th of January).
- According to the target audience (more important for end users) there is the possibility to create small websites in local languages with a summary of the project information. The idea is that in every “local” website there will be a link that links to the main one with all the project information. The partners are in charge of the translation.
- Clear templates need to be provided by the WP5 leaders to ask input from partners in a specific and targeted way. Not only what is needed in terms of content, but also how it needs to be delivered.
- The website will be created by the middle of next week (approximately 16-17 of January) and the link will have as an end both “.eu” and “.com”.
- Focus of communication and dissemination WP: promote the database! The partners will have to focus on promoting the database to farmers instead of focusing only in the creation of it.

AFTERNOON

WP2 (USC) Compile and evaluate EIP-AGRI Knowledge Reservoir (TNs) outputs

From **13.30 to 16.00** WP2 discussions.

Rosa Mosquera, WP2 leader made a presentation (Annex 15: WP2 Compile and evaluate EIP-AGRI Knowledge Reservoir (TNs) outputs presentation (1st day)) explaining that this WP starts with the initial analysis of the Thematic Networks (22 plus those approved in 2018). The WP consist of four tasks lead by different leaders:

- Task 2.1: Identify the key partners and responsible people for the different activities (IT, communication, dissemination, etc.) in each TN. Analyse and collect the type of data and the ways data are produced, collected and stored in the current H2020 TNs. Task leader

USC.

Partners who volunteered are welcome to complete the google sheet with contact details ASAP before end of the month.

- Task 2.2: Evaluate the format and design of KRs (as open sources) within current and past TN networks and related H2020 multi-actor projects. Task leader IDELE.
- Task 2.3: Assess the dissemination and communication activities, materials and tools on their respective impact towards the end users, farmers, foresters and advisors, used by TNs. Task leader ACTA.
- Task 2.4: Analyse the multi-actor approach used by TNs in the short, medium and long term. To approach different actors, we should have only one common standardized and harmonized approach, including one brand, one elevator pitch and the same messages (to promote EURAKNOS). Task leader GLZ.

For the interviews, they will have to be done possibly by April.

- Task 2.5: Exchange and compile the experiences and know-how of the TNs with focus on the end-user groups: farmers, foresters and advisors. Task leader AU.

Task 2.1 is in charge of the preliminary evaluation of the content and organization of the data based on regions, sectors, topics and management aspects addressed. It will collect and analyse the data that are currently available on the website.

Task 2.2., 2.3, 2.4 will make an initial desk-study analysis of the format and design of the Knowledge reservoir (Task 2.2), dissemination and communication activities (Task 2.3) and the multi-actor approach (Task 2.4). While Task 2.5 will be a jointly report of all of them.

Rosa showed an initial excel to be discussed, and showed that for the first task the content will be analysed but also the relationship of this content to the main aspects of EIP-Agri related to H2020 (multiactor approach projects) and to the Rural Development Programmes (Operational Groups). A decision was taken to further develop the tables by all task leaders. Also a table with the contacts of the coordinators and the relevant WP leaders of the different TNs to be analysed was launched and assigned to the knowledge reservoir, communication and dissemination and the multi-actor approach.

Afterwards the group was split in four smaller groups. Each group discussed about one specific topic (Data, IT, Communication and Dissemination, MAA):

[Workshop on Task 2.1 - Data impact assessment of TNs, Task Leader: USC](#)

In the Task 2.1 the conclusion was to evaluate the content of all produced material, we will start with the TNs and we will investigate the possibilities to include some of the MA and OG. There was a long discussion of the definition of 'data'. Data means in Euraknos all kind of different types of end user materials used by institutes to educate and demonstrate farmers on how to improve the sustainability of their practices (farmers and foresters). An example on how to collect and analyse materials was presented by Timea. It is concluded to take her example as a template to start the desk top study.

Workshop on Task 2.2 Design of knowledge reservoirs within current and past, Task Leader: IDELE

This working group, focused mostly on technical issues about data acquisition for the needs of the EURAKNOS project. More specifically, an issue that arose had to do with the form and format of data that can be made available from TNs' data stores. Data sources, which can be either semi-structured or unstructured, may have been created in a range of software applications (ranging from text editors to spreadsheet creation applications) and can be available in various digital formats (e.g. spreadsheets, text documents, csv files, pdf files, etc.). This fact poses significant challenges in terms of data acquisition, integration into a central repository and processing. Another issue of importance is associated with the way in which data is stored in TNs' data stores. It is necessary to have access to TNs' data stores designs so as to be able to figure out the logical schemas that have been employed for giving structure to stored data. Resolution of this issue may require contact with database administrators and/or designers/developers. Within this context, another issue that was brought to discussion related to whose property is the available data. Although this fact was not the main focus of the IT working group, data governance and intellectual property rights are also matters of concern in terms of design and development of data integration processes. Question lists regarding issues of technical nature, when interviewing representatives of TNs, will offer significant help to their efficient resolution.

Workshop on Task 2.3- Communication, dissemination and education, Task Leader ACTA

Who will do the desktop study? All partners have a list and they are welcome to discuss on Slack. Slack will be one of the main communication tools for EURAKNOS to avoid too much email traffic; documents are placed on the google drive. Task 2.3...

- will look for communication and dissemination strategies and indicators
- will inform for the Communication and Dissemination plan of the TNs
- will collect the numbers and results of communication of TNs
- will have a common table (google drive). With excel it will be possible to make charts afterwards.
- will probably propose Mesydel as a methodology. This has to be confirmed first. ¹
- will distribute the work over the partners involved in the task: three TNs per partner
- will develop a template for the desktop study and questionnaires
- will follow a timeline:
 - desktop study finished for M3
 - interviews April to end of June
 - workshop in M8

Who will do interviews? ACTA/RAU. Some questions raised.

- Are we doing interviews with 1 people by TN or more? There is a need for an overview of the people that will be interviewed and by whom (interact with other task leaders)
- Can we harmonize the interviews (in order to avoid duplication)?
- Can we address the questions accordingly from the identified strategies?
- How many questions are needed and workable? It depends to how many tools are used.

¹ Mesydel - Conducting an online Delphi survey

Originally, the mediation method known as the Delphi method is a paper-based method. This method makes it possible, with a process in several rounds, to obtain a list of positions — and even a consensus — by questioning a panel of experts of a given field. Between each round, the mediator draws conclusions, then launches a new round with questions inspired by these conclusions. At the end of the process, a report is prepared detailing the positions.

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- Can we use skype for the face to face interviews?

Questions (qualitative, quantitative) to be asked during F2F (face-to-face) interviews. The starting point will be the table 1.3 on the DoA.

- What did /didn't work during the dissemination and communication activities?
- Why? What is/was the impact of the TN communication and dissemination?
- What are the farmers' favourite communication and dissemination tools?
- Quantitative questions based on the desktop study are
 - What is the number of people targeted and reached?
- Qualitative questions:
 - What is the uptake of the results by the end users.
- Open questions:
 - What did effectively work?
 - What would you advice for a TN?
 - What you didn't do but you should do now?
 - What is the relation with EIP-AGRI ?

Next to consortium partners responsible to communicate and disseminate to end-users, it seems interesting to contact end users themselves. The question rises if it would be possible to have face to face interviews with them also? A first step is to add them in the table of contacts.

[Workshop on Task 2.4: Multi-actor approach, Task Leader: GLZ](#)

During this workshop, major questions were discussed regarding the multi-actor approach (MAA) of TNs. The group elaborated on some key questions (quantitative/qualitative) that could be either solved during the desk-top study preliminary work, or be part of the F2F interviews. These main questions are displayed below, as bullet points:

- Which sector?
- Who are the involved types of actors?
- How many types or which categories of end users/actors (MA) exist?
- Are certain types of MA missing in a TN project and why?
- What are sector-specific considerations and sector independent considerations to fulfil a MAA?
- Why and how was each type of MA approached to become part of the TN?
- Why was each type of MA interested to join (motivation) the TN?
- Were MA already involved in other TNs before?
- What were the barriers (e.g. stakeholder fatigue) to participate in a TN?
- How do different types of MA contribute (create content or only use as end-user) in a TN?
- Which topics in the TN are tackled by which actors and why?
- From when to when is the involvement of MA in a TN (start to finish or mapped in time)?
- Define/explain the MAA chosen for the TN (e.g. EC is still lacking comprehensive information or analysis what MAA actually varies across projects, regions, sectors)? For example including a question such as can clarify: When were you designing your TN. How/in which way were you thinking of this multi-actor approach and involvement while writing the project proposal? Have initial expectations changed during the project/after the project? What worked well and what didn't work in realisation of this thinking during the course of the process? What are lessons learned – how would you approach it now?

- How/has involvement of multi-actors changed over the project? Why? (How did the MAA situation change from before the project to just after the project and to several years after the project (long-term MAA sustainability)?)
- How many links were you able to make to other MA projects and groups in the EIP-Agri landscape (focus groups, operational groups, rural development networks etc.). How would you describe this process (main difficulties and suggestions/actions taken to facilitate this process)? What have been the main reasons for these linkages (e.g. use of it in future projects, advisory services etc.).
- What are the lessons learned from experienced MA projects. How do they approach things different when they would start up a new TN or MA project?
- What were the benefits for each type of MA for being involved in the project?
- Which results/outputs are available? How did each type of MA benefit from the outputs of the project in the short, medium and long term?

For task 2.4 it seems crucial to design oriented interviews for target groups, with specific questions which have to be adapted to audience. Therefore, we might have to perform 3 to 4 types of interviews (farmers oriented/ advisors oriented/ research oriented/industries oriented)

Further/additional key information for task 2.4 could be:

- What communication/dissemination channels have been mostly used and developed between all actors and throughout the timeline?
- From where do you normally get your:
 - Information on topics actual for what you work with?
 - News from the sector?
 - Contact to people who can advise or help you?

Elaboration of a template with columns by the end of February /March 2019. The data will be shared on google drive.

Branding Workshop

The last workshop of the day, led by LF regarded the brand of the project (Branding workshop). The workshop started with the explanation of branding: the strategic approach and the visual representation of the brand. The brand has to be simple, open, and collaborative. Afterwards people were invited to make value exercise detailed value exercise and visual exercise in groups. Everyone was free to express his opinion and to give suggestions. (Annex 16: Branding workshop)

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1_W8-Ota_hD_6XX4ZtAqEkSLeodljcv2

SECOND DAY

People present at the meeting the second day:

Present: Maria-Jose A., Inge V.O. (EC), Luc P. (Copa-Cogeca), Nevena A. (FAO), Andrew F. (AKI), Tom K. via telecom (TEAGASC), Pieter S., Nathan D.G., Lies H., Elena F. (UGent), Sylvia B. (Agrolink Flanders/EV ILVO), Els B., Alexander O. (PS KW), Patrick S., Maxime M. (IDELE), Lisa Williams v.D. (RAU), Spyros F., Hercules P. (AUA), Maria Rosa M.L., Nuria F.D. (USC), Elodie P., Franz J.M., (GLZ), Davino V.H., (LFG), Szabolcs V., Csaba P., Szilveszter P. (AKI), Andrew L. (IFA), Ilse A.R., Merete S. (ICROFS AU), Timea R. (NAK), Pauline B. (ACTA), Konstantin M., Pille K. (ARC), Bram M. (IFOAM EU)

Excused: Jessica S. (RAU), Andre L. (GODAN).

Not present: Helga W. (FIBL), Jannes M. (CEJA).

From **9.00 to 10.50**, project partners, strategic innovation board and EC project offices introduced themselves.

WP2 (USC) Presentation by Maria Rosa M.L. (Annex 17: WP2 Compile and evaluate EIP-AGRI Knowledge Reservoir (TNs) outputs presentation (2nd day))

From **10.50 to 11.05**

After the presentation the following discussion took place:

Everybody agrees that F2F interviews have a lot of value. Not only desktop study about the final sugar coated output. Also include lessons learned, why did something not go well, missing data in the final output.

Once all the contacts have been identified we need to look for synergies in approach and combine interviews if possible. We also need a standardized approach to promote the project (elevator pitch) among the TN partners. This should answer why they would help us and what is in it for them.

WP3 (IDELE) Presentation by Patrick S. (Annex 18: WP3 Design a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR))

The WP 3 aims to co-design a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR) and the designing of the platform. This part appeared to be relevant by its central position between the state of art built in the WP2 and the construction of the Knowledge reservoir by itself (WP4).

The first review of Thematic Network sites revealed a significant diversity of contents (fact sheet, video, languages etc.) and architecture of those platforms.

Different items needs to be explored such as, the type of data (technological information, economic information, and practical issues and end-users comments) and their management (collection, storage, quality analysis, sharing etc.).

Specifications will explore:

- The customer demand : with customer segments, personae characteristics;
- Core skills : the value proposition, newness, performance and customization;

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- Informatics skills: database management, digital language and supports and digital technics;
- Marketing skills: product quality, distribution channel and promotional strategy;
- Maintenance: customer assistance , hot line and back office maintenance;

Thus, it will define the best methodologies and practices to collect, generate and store knowledge data outputs of TNs.

The HIKR architecture will be designed (from back to front office, internal and external links, and rights and profiles regarding functionality and data uses). It will help to design the common format and tools (software, data formats) to be used for a HIKR adapted for advisory services and farmers and foresters. This part will provide partners with the platform specifications. More precisely, it will select the main tools to disseminate, communicate and to inform end-users within the HIKR but also through EIP-AGRI and TN platforms.

Finally, the best practices and methods will be defined to foster the multi-actor approach for the production of knowledge (team building, training, tools and stakeholders' engagement).

After the presentation the following discussion took place:

- How will we evaluate which are the most relevant data?
- We will need to look at potential good examples outside of the TNs.
- FAO organized a workshop on this and developed an approach with good practices and a repository will launch in 02/19: <https://www.wearenet.eu/>. Nevena A. will send the background documents.
- Elodie P. will upload the CASA reports on TN best practices in communication and dissemination.

WP4 (AUA) presentation by Spyros F. (Annex 19: WP4 Explore an e-Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP))

After the presentation the following questions raised.

- Where will the platform be hosted? At UGent?
- How will we get the data into the e-HIKR? In which WP? Will we use some web crawler software? It will depend on WP2 interviews.

For what concerns the maintenance and the sustainability, a possibility to go into two directions is proposed.

- I. A solution in connection with the CAP network and financing from the CAP (terms of references are needed to be discussed). The EIP-Agri Service Point already hosts the repository for the practice abstracts.
- II. A solution to develop the platform for future projects in Horizon Europe.

WP5 (IfA) presentation by Andrew L. (Annex 14: WP5 communication plan presentation)

After the presentation the following questions were discussed.

- Leverage the outreach network of the thematic networks (e.g. on twitter 30 x 300).
- What is the approach and expectation for the SIB for the vision paper?
- Deliver 100 instead of 120 practice abstracts as output. 20 in year 1 and 80 in year 2.

- Big communication activities need to be reported in advance to the EC.

SIB POINTS OF VIEW

As the last part of the kick off meeting SIBs were invited to give their comments and suggestions about EURAKNOS project and its challenges. The overall opinion was that in general, the project is well structured, useful and ambitious. Below more details are reported.

Andrew Fielsend (AKI, Hungary): “It is a good idea to look at what to do and do not do, but keep it simple. The work plan is very logically structured, the team is very competent and has previous work experience. TNs are extremely successful but are all very different. We have to further improve with better practices. The outputs of this project will be very valuable, however the sustainability is a big challenge and should be addressed. We can learn from other ongoing initiatives, also at national level. It is also important to connect with Eastern Central European Countries to stimulate a geographical cross-over. The sustainability is directly linked to the impact of the work being done with EURAKNOS, it is an added value.”

Nevena Alexandrova (FAO, Rome):

“Achieving the goal of an EU wide knowledge reservoir is important. FAO has a vast experience with knowledge reservoirs. The sustainability will require particular efforts; the knowledge availability and accessibility will change over time, this should be taken into account from the very start of the project, a clear vision on this is needed. Having the right instruments is a challenge for IT, there are many TNs and OGs. How to manage a tool that brings value for a wide variety of farmers with so diverse interests? Recently FAO had an expert consultation on the needs and the criteria of data collection for small holder and family farms (<https://www.wearenet.eu/events-news/detail/regional-expert-consultation/>). Two technical papers came out of it that are in particular relevant to WP3 and WP 4 and partially WP2 (<http://www.fao.org/in-action/kore/news-and-events/news-details/en/c/881412/>).”

Tom Kelly (EUFRAS):

“TNs have to closely work together towards achieving their objectives and bring added value of TNs. WP2 and WP3 will guide TNs to bring this added value. “

Luc Peeters (COPA –COGECA, Brussels):

“The project is ambitious, only 23.5 months left to perform the work and achieve the objectives. This however doable because most of the consortium members have a vast experience in TNs. End-users of EURAKNOS output is the farming community. The first step is to harmonise and standardise TNs. The timing is ambitious, but doable since you have a good team.”

Inge Van Oost (DG AGRI)

“The project will have a strong added value when linked to existing channels, advisory bodies, organisations such as EUFRAS. We also can learn from ongoing initiatives, we have to listen to their experiences. In the SWG AKIS there are members with such an experience e.g. Jaime Sio Torres who works for the region of Cataluña and who is strongly involved in rural development

programmes. Local communicators will have an important role and also the interoperability of the projects' results (knowledge reservoir) with existing initiatives, using existing dissemination and strategic innovation channels will be key to the success and impact of EURAKNOS. We rely on the IT specialists in particular for interoperability issues."

ANNEX

Annex 1: UGent presentation

EURAKNOS

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EURAKNOS PROJECT

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2

EURAKNOS SUBJECT TN-PROJECT DATA

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3

EURAKNOS SUBJECT TN-PROJECT DATA

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4

EURAKNOS GOAL - HIKR

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5

EURAKNOS COLLABORATORS – PIETER S

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6

EURAKNOS Q&I MANAGER – NATHAN DG

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EURAKNOS NETWORK MGR – SYLVIA B

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EURAKNOS PHD – ELENA FEO

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EURAKNOS FIN. – BJORN VDK AND LIEVE H

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10

EURAKNOS PRACTICAL ISSUES – LIES H

"The Euraknos project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863"

11

**Dept.
Plants
and
Crops**

The Laboratory of Crop Protection Chemistry, as part of the department of Plants and Crops is particularly experienced in the study of pesticide residues in crops and environmental samples (soil, water and air), pesticide formulation and the study of side effects of pesticide treatments.

"The Euraknos project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863"

Pieter Spanoghe

Professor

DEPARTMENT OF
PLANTS AND CROPS

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 Ghent University
 @ugent
 Ghent University

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Annex 2: PSKW presentation

Our goals:

1. Practical & applied scientific research
2. Interact with all actors involved in horticulture
(growers – research - technology suppliers
advisors - policy makers, ...)
3. Act as dissemination channel

Euraknos consortium members:

Els Berckmoes

Alexander Opdebeeck

Our themes:

FERTINNOWA Thematic Network

Transfer of INNOvative techniques for sustainable Water use in fertigated crops

Annex 3: IDELE presentation

Idele French Livestock Institute

R&D organization

at the crossroad between research and advisory functions
mandate to improve the competitiveness of herbivore
farming and value chains.

& generate technical solutions to bovine, sheep, goat and
equine breeders and stakeholders.

**PREPARING FOR
TOMORROW'S
GENETICS**

Accelerating the selection processes and widening the range of criteria: health, feeding efficiency, environmental impact...

**OPTIMIZING
ANIMAL
HUSBANDRY**

Optimizing fodder production, feeding, reproduction, farm housing, farm mechanization and equipment...

**ADDING
PRODUCT VALUE**

Meeting agro-industry demands and farm-to-fork quality requirements...

**IMPROVING
PROFITABILITY**

Improving profitability of farms and agro-industries, Strengthening value chains efficiency...

**EASING
BREEDERS'S LIFE
AND LABOUR**

Developing attractiveness of animal farming, fostering employment, matching workload and herd sizes...

**An internal organization based on cross-disciplinary
approaches facilitating exchanges and knowledge
construction**

**& a regional deployment serving territories and French
livestock diversity**

Expert support, project assistance, data and tools management...

Idele.fr

Annex 4: RAU presentation

Royal Agricultural University

- A campus-based university, established in 1845, with 1,200 students
- Oldest agricultural education institution in the English speaking world, still at the forefront of agricultural education

RAU Catalyst programme

- Developed with industry
- Skills focussed & work ready
- Postgraduate – from Sept 2019
 - MSc Sustainable Food and Agriculture Policy
 - MBA Innovation in Sustainable Food and Agriculture
 - Distance learning & short residential blocks
- Undergraduate – from Sept 2020
 - BSc Business and Innovation BA Human Geography with Food Ethics

20/02/2019

08 May 2019

RAU to meet post-Brexit needs of agri-food and land management sectors through innovative multimillion pound initiative

The Royal Agricultural University (RAU) has today (8 May) announced a new £2.5m initiative to help meet the needs of the land management and agri-food sectors in the post-Brexit era.

The plan will see the RAU and its academic partners the **Cambridge and Community Research Institute (CCRI)** at the University of Gloucestershire and **University College of Food Management (UCFM)** join with industry stakeholders to drive future success in sustainable land management and food production.

RAU Knowledge Hub: KE programme

GOV.UK

Home > The Cabinet for Food, Fisheries and the Environment Policy Statement (2020)

Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs

Policy paper
Health and Harmony: the future for food, farming and the environment in a Green Brexit - policy statement
 Updated 14 September 2019

Our ambition for the future of food, farming and the environment

British farmers, growers and foresters play a vital role in protecting the countryside, while producing world class food, plants and trees. From now we will use the opportunity of leaving the EU to transform how these sectors can enhance the environment and get a fair return for their goods.

Under our **Green Brexit 2020** we will spend public money on:

- enriching wildlife habitats
- preventing flooding
- improving the quality of air
- soil and peat
- and planting trees

What we do :

- Rural **collaborative policy**
- Rural **innovation support**
- Rural **enterprise acceleration**

Professor David Main

Dr. Jessica Stokes

Dr. Lisa van Dijk

2/26/2019

Annex 5: USC presentation

LUGO CAMPUS

EURAKNOS

>25000 students
>150 degrees and masters

Escuela Politécnica Superior
Campus de Lugo, Lugo, Spain
Grupo de Investigación de Sistemas Silvopastorales
E-mails: mrosa.mosquera.losada@usc.es
antonio.rigueiro@usc.es
nuria.ferreiro@usc.es

Teaching and research activities of over 40 years

Agroforestry

(INIA: SoSSCeCa; CICYT: AFCLIMA; EU: AGFORWARD; Open2preserve)

NETWORKING

- Current president of the Spanish Agroforestry Association
- Coordinator of AFINET
- Coordinator of a SUPRA REGIONAL Operational Group
- Chair of the Crop Production Research Group of the Global Research Alliance
- Chair of the "enabling environment" of the Global Alliance for Climate Smart Agriculture (FAO)

Bioeconomy

Common Agr

Land use
Pillar I and Pillar II
Policy recommendations

Innovation (EU: AGFORWARD; EU: AFINET; EURAKNOS; AF Supraoperational group)

Annex 6: GLZ presentation

**Grassland Centre
Lower Saxony/Bremen**

EURAKNOS Kick-off meeting
Date: 10/1/19- 11/1/19

Grassland Centre Lower Saxony/Bremen

Aim: to enhance the multifunctionality of grassland

Registered association (e.V.) since 2012 emerged from two-year project phase (45 members)

Actively involved in major European networks

Platform for cooperation and innovation transfer

Currently 9 national/3 international projects:

GLZ Board (13), from different interest groups of the grassland Agriculture in Lower Saxony /Bremen

15 employees, based in Ovelgönne (Lower Saxony)

The GLZ Team

Dr. Arno Krause, executive director

Key Partners

Key International Projects

Framework topics

Annex 7: AKI presentation

Introduction of AKI and its role in agricultural information production

Szabolcs Vágó, PhD

Brussels, 10-11 January 2019

www.aki.gov.hu

Introduction of AKI

- Main centre of agricultural economics research in Hungary
- A key background institution of the Ministry of Agriculture
- Staff number: 131; 43 PhD or ongoing PhD studies.
- More than 60 years of agricultural policy analysis (since 1954)

Main tasks of AKI

Research

- Sustainable bio-economy and policy evaluation
- Natural resource management in agriculture
- Resource-efficient agri-food value chains
- Rural development and programme evaluation
- Development opportunities in aquaculture

Operation of information systems

- Agricultural Statistical Information System (ASIR)
- Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN)
- Market Price Information System (MPIS)

Research projects
FP 7 (2 completed)
H2020 (5 ongoing)

Capacity building projects
EC EuropeAid
EC Twinning
TAIEX, FAO

Main publications

- Agro-economic Books, Studies and Information series
- Farming (Gazdálkodás)
- Studies in Agricultural Economics
- Bulletins on Agricultural Markets
- FADN Yearbook
- Information on Agricultural Markets
- Statistical reports

AKI EURAKNOS TEAM

Szabolcs Vágó, PhD Main point of contact, AKI team leader	Szilveszter Palotay Expert Task 4.2.	Csaba Pesti Expert Task 4.1.	László Barnafi Coder	Zoltán Szabó Coder	Gergely Szabó Admin contact
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	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	Total
Person-months	1			12		13
WP4	Explore a e-Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP)					
T4.1	Feasibility and added value of an e-KRP					
T4.2	Design and development of a prototype e-KRP					

Research Institute of Agricultural Economics

www.aki.gov.hu

Annex 8: ICROFS AU presentation

International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems (ICROFS)

What do we do?

**Contribute to the development of a market
driven and competitive organic sector
through research and development**

- *Coordinate* the national Danish research programmes
- *Coordinate* the EU research network CORE Organic
- *Communicate* organic research results and knowledge from the Danish and EU programmes and in general
- *Participate in research projects and thematic networks* as coordinator, participant or with responsibilities for communication and involvement and engagement of stakeholder (national and international)
- *Promote research* in organic food systems and the development of *research agendas*

Ilse A. Rasmussen, Helene Uller-Kristensen, Merete Studnitz

- M. Sc. Agronomy
- Researcher
- Weed management
- Organic Eprints
- Coordinator Danish Research Progr.
- OK-NET Arable
- OK-NET EcoFeed
- VOA3R

- Cand. Ling.merc
- Communic. officer
- Communication, dissemination, knowledge transfer
- Public websites
- Social media
- Knowledge platforms
- Articles, Newsletters
- videos

- Agronomist, Ph.D.
- Researcher Behaviour- welfare
- Advisor – pigs Conv. – organic
- Best practice manual, farmers
- Farmer field schools
- OK-NET EcoFeed

Annex 9: ACTA presentation

Acta-les instituts techniques agricoles

About Acta: Agricultural Technical Institutes

Agricultural Technical Institutes (known by their French initials, ITAs) are professional tools for applied research and transfer, specialised by sector (field crops, livestock, fruit and vegetables, viticulture, specialised production (horticulture, medicinal plants, tropical plants, algae etc.), organic agriculture). Acta, leads this network, bringing them together and promoting their expertise in the field and their unique know-how in France and abroad. Collectively, this network is a model for supporting competitive and sustainable innovation and amplifies value creation within territories, agricultural sectors and agroindustrial companies.

Follow Acta on :

www.acta.asso.fr

[@Acta_asso](https://twitter.com/Acta_asso)

www.acta.asso.fr/linkedin

[Acta channel](#)

[Booklet on H2020 projects.](#)

Europe Contact: europa@acta.asso.fr

IFV - Institut français de la vigne et du vin

The French institute for vine and wine is a scientific and technical organisation supporting all actors in the wine sector, benefiting from the double qualification of Agricultural Technical Institute and Agri-food Technical Institute. IFV is one of the main actors in the national agricultural rural development programme and its research and innovation structural policies over the 2014-2020 period. The 140 IFV staff (ampelographers, agronomists, geneticists, oenologists and microbiologists) develop their work in around 20 units across France's various wine production areas.

Website: <http://www.vignevin.com/en/english.html>

Management contact: Jean-Pierre Van Ruyskensvelde, direction@vignevin.com

Europe contact: Eirios Hugo, eirios.hugo@vignevin.com

Acta & IFV in Euraknos project

- Implication in all WPs with a focus on communication activities (Acta) and TNs experience (IFV)
- Lead of the **T2.3 - Dissemination, communication and information strategies**
- Lead of the **T5.1 – Communication activities**

Pauline BODIN
Communication analysis

Eric Serrano & Eirios Hugo
Winetwork coordination

Annex 10: ARC presentation

 PÕLLUMAJANDUSUURINGUTE KESKUS
AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH CENTRE

AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH CENTRE (ARC)

- ✓ **Estonian Agricultural Research Centre is a state agency under the Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs that is responsible for providing laboratory and field testing services (agro-chemistry, plant health and microbiology; seed testing; residues and contaminants; plant production) to agricultural producers, scientific institutions, governmental supervisory bodies and other clients.**
- ✓ **ARC is also one of the main advisory bodies in Estonia in the field of Rural Development and plays a central role in the evaluation (internal and external) of the Rural Development Policy by conducting different fields of studies regarding agri-environment and rural economy.**
- ✓ **Coordination of farmers' and advisors' compulsory and voluntary trainings for approximately 6,000 farmers in the frame of RDP - main focus on agri-environment (soil, water, biodiversity) and cross-compliance issues.**
- ✓ **Since January 2018 Estonian Rural Network (NRN) is also operating and coordinating its activities under ARC via Rural Networks' Department who is acting as a National Rural Network Support Unit (NSU) for Estonia at EU level.**

ARC Team

Pille Koorberg
pille.koorberg@pmk.agri.ee

Hanna Tamsalu
hanna.tamsalu@pmk.agri.ee

Konstantin Mihhejev
konstantin.mihhejev@pmk.agri.ee

Reve Lambur
Reve.lambur@pmk.agri.ee

Annex 11: IFOAM EU presentation

Bram Moeskops

Yulia Barabanova

Kata Gócs

What is IFOAM EU?

- IFOAM EU is the European regional group of IFOAM – Organics International
- Represents more than 190 members in all the 28 EU Member States and associated countries
- Organic farming associations
- Organic food processors, retailers, traders
- Organic food and farming advisors and researchers
- Organic certifiers
- Headquarters in Brussels (Belgium)

Annex 12: AUA presentation

Precision Agriculture group Agricultural University of Athens

Spyros Fountas / Hercules Panoutsopoulos/Katerina Kasimati

EURAKNOS Research team

Associate Professor Spyros Fountas, is Editor-in-Chief in the ELSEVIER journal “Computers and Electronics in Agriculture” (IF: 2.45) and he is in the Editorial Board at the Precision Agriculture journal, since 2011. He holds an MSc from Cranfield University UK in Information Technology, and PhD from Copenhagen University, Denmark in Systems Analysis on Precision Agriculture.

Hercules has a BSc degree in Mathematics from the Dpt. of Mathematics of the National & Kapodistrian University of Athens and an MSc degree in e-Learning from the Dpt. of Digital Systems of the University of Piraeus. He is database developer and data analytics

Aikaterini Kasimati has worked in postharvest handling, bioenvironmental engineering, water resources management and energy production. In May 2015, got her M.S. in Agricultural and Biological Engineering at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, USA. She has also held intern positions in John Deere, in Illinois, Hvarske Vode, Croatia

Group Research projects

- **Smart-AKIS** “European Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) towards innovation-driven research in Smart Farming Technology” 2016-2018. **Coordinator.**
- **GATES** “Applying GAMing TEchnologies for training professionals in Smart Farming. 2017-2019. **Coordinator.**
- **OPTIMA** “Optimised Integrated Pest Management for precise detection and control of plant diseases in perennial crops and open-field vegetables. 2018-2022. **Coordinator.**
- **APOLLO** “Advisory platform for small farms based on earth observation“. 2017-2019. **WP Leader.**
- **IoF2020** “Internet of farm and food 2020” 2017-2020. **Technology Chair for Fruits and Vines.**

Outline

- REA
- Policy Context
- Boosting Impact
- Implementation
- Financial Aspects

REA

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REA B2 - H2020 - Societal Challenge 2

What is our role?

- **PO:** Maria José Amaral / **AFO:** Danielle Epis
- Provide support and advice
- Follow-up implementation, assess reports and deliverables
- Order interims and final payments
- Communication (Art. 52)
 - Through the Coordinator via the PP (formal) or e-mail (informal)
 - Electronic submission (and signature)

Every 3 months short e-mail with actual progress (activities in progress, planning, deviations, relevant events)

Horizon 2020

- Contribute to [Junckers' Priorities](#)

- Contribute to [Commissioner Moedas R&I Priorities](#)

Horizon 2020 focus on Impact & Innovation

- **Results used** to address strategic challenges and contribute to the **expected impacts**
- **Any type of innovation** - new products, services, organisational or business methods, improved networks or collaborations, etc
- **Any type of benefit and impact** – financial, societal, research, environmental, technical, commercial, educational

Rural Renaissance Call

- Smarter, greener, more circular and better connected rural areas
- Boost innovation systems, co-creation and better use of knowledge by investing in networks, skills development and advisory systems
- Support implementation of:

Thematic Networks

- collect existing knowledge and best practices
- transform into practical information
- make available to all

Thematic Networks lead to a better uptake of existing solutions across Europe

The infographic features a map of Europe on the left with a network of nodes (lightbulbs and question marks) connected by lines. On the right, a group of four people are seated at a table, engaged in a discussion. Above them are icons for a lightbulb, a question mark, and a stork. To the right of the group, a 'Practice abstract' document is shown, with arrows pointing to a laptop, a tablet, and a mail icon, indicating the dissemination of information.

Thematic Networks - Expected Impacts

- Close the research and innovation gap
- Collect and distribute easily accessible practice-oriented knowledge
- Improve professional skills and competences
- Increase the flow of information in Europe
- Improve user acceptance of collected solutions and dissemination of knowledge

Impacts everywhere...

- **Expected impacts** in work programme
- Impact criterion during **evaluation**
- Impact related articles in **Grant Agreement**: Art. 20, Art. 23, Art. 28, Art. 29
- Impacts documented in **Periodic and Final Reports**
- Communication, **dissemination and exploitation of results**
- **REA policy feedback activities**

What is your project intervention logic?

Impact monitoring to do list

- Take your **impact indicators** seriously
- Test your project's underlying 'intervention logic'. Review (& revise)
- Have an appropriate **monitoring and evaluation approach** – quantify your results and impact - justify choice of baselines, benchmarks, assumptions, references & calculations
- Consider attribution to the project
- Provide analysis if impacts are not achieved
- **Use dissemination & exploitation of results activities to maximise impacts**

Boosting impact

What are project results?

Tangible or intangible outputs of the action

e.g. inventions, prototypes, services, knowledge, technology, processes, networks, data whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected

- **What is special about your results?**
- **Identify key exploitable results or outputs** which can be used and create impact, either by project partners or other stakeholders
- If results are **not used** -> expected impacts will **not be achieved**

Communication (Art. 38)

Promotion of **the action and its results to multiple audiences** (including the media and the general public) to show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities

- **Think, Plan, Act** – What do you want to achieve?
 - Set clear communication objectives and indicators
 - Use pertinent messages, right medium and means
 - Monitor effectiveness, re-think, re-plan...
- You can't reach everyone
- Think issue, not project - Make it relevant to everyday life, **show impact on society** – Good use of public money
- **Think Global – Act Local**
- Be creative – vamp up the visual, reduce the writing

EC Communication channels and activities (multipliers)

- Inform us before of any major communication activity
- Make use of our communication channels

#H2020 #ResearchImpactEU #EIPagri #HorizonEU #InvestEUresearch

EC Communication channels and activities (multipliers)

Success Stories

The most recent Success stories from EU Research. Select a theme or country from the menus on the left to see more articles

- Targeting fish parasites for a healthier aquaculture industry

EU-funded marine scientists are fighting fish parasites in farmed fish by developing new strategies and technologies to prevent their spread and ensure high-quality seafood for consumers.
Published: 12 July 2020

Bio-based innovation builds Europe's bioeconomy

A global transition from an economy dominated by petrochemical-based processes towards ones that are sustainable, bio-based and circular, is now underway. In this context bio-based innovation has the potential to help to build a bioeconomy that will reduce the European economy's dependence on fossil feedstocks by using CO2 instead, thereby making a positive contribution to meeting the EU's climate goals, while relieving pressure on ecosystems and helping to create 'green jobs'.

EC Communication channels and activities (multipliers)

- Promote your project and results on the EIP website, newsletter, factsheets, magazine and social media
- Promote your events on the European agriculture innovation calendar

servicepoint@eip-agri.eu

Dissemination (Art. 29)

Transfer of knowledge and results in a targeted way to audiences that can potentially **use** them (e.g. scientific community, industry, professional organisations, policymakers).

- **Make sure to comply with the obligation to protect (Art.27)...** then disseminate
 - Who are the key targets (relevant stakeholders and potential end-users)?
 - What are the key messages?
 - How will you deliver the messages?
 - How can results be accessed and under what terms?
- **Scientific work and results** are openly available in an easily accessible, understandable and re-usable form
- **Policy-relevant results** should be flagged and brought to the attention of the appropriate bodies

Communication versus Dissemination

Exploitation (Art. 28)

Use of project results during and after the project implementation – for commercial purposes, in further research activities, to improve policies, and/or for tackling economic and societal problems – **by project partners or end-users**

- Make use of the results – credible **Exploitation roadmap and strategy**
- **Recognise the landscape** – existing knowledge or solutions, market issues, regulations, competitors, standards
- What **barriers or enablers** (standards, IPRs, regulatory, ethical)?
- When relevant **ensure interoperability** and **long-term sustainability** / financial sustainability

What? How?

H2020 Programme

AGA – Annotated Model Grant Agreement

"The Euraknos project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863"

Reporting

Reporting and Reviews (Art. 20 and 22)

- **Periodic Report:** clear, informative and concise account of the activities during the reporting period (against the GA baseline)
 - Technical report and financial statements submitted electronically as a **single package**
 - What did you do? What did you achieve? How did you tackle potential issues (R&D, market barriers, IPR)? Any deviations? Corrective measures?
 - How have resources been used?
- **Review:** in-depth examination of implementation after each reporting period supported by external experts
 - Contradictory Review procedure

Reporting and Reviews (Art. 20 and 22)

- **Continuous Reporting**

Summary for publication	Deliverables Ethics, DMP, Other Reports	Milestones	Critical Risks	Publications	Disseminat...	Patents (IPR)	Innovation	SME Impact	Open Data	Gender	ABS Regulation

- **Deliverables:**

- To be submitted at the specified timing, ongoing revision and at review
- If a deliverable is going to be late, explain the reason, the corrective action undertaken and the estimated date of delivery
- Public deliverables will appear in CORDIS

Amendments

Amendments **may not result in changes that** — if known before awarding the grant — **would have had an impact on the decision to award the project**

- Consult informally the PO as soon as possible
- Prepared electronically
- Group changes (but request is agreed or rejected as a whole)
- Explain the situation: **Keep it simple – straight to the point!**
- Agreement of the consortium

Recruitment and working conditions (Art. 32) and Gender Equality (Art. 33)

- Take measures to implement the **European Charter** for Researchers and **Code of Conduct** for the Recruitment of Researchers
- **Proactively aim** – to the extent possible – for **gender balance** at all levels (explain deviations in periodic and final report)
- **Best practices:**
 - Staff should be recruited based on merit in an open and transparent way
 - Staff should have access to training and career development
 - Mobility should not adversely affect working conditions

Ethical Principles (Art. 34)

- The beneficiaries must carry out the action in compliance with:
 - ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity)
 - applicable international, EU and national law
- Ethics deliverables submitted according to GA. Necessary authorizations need to be obtained prior to start of the activity
- Consult the PO if unforeseen research activities that may raise ethics issues are needed

EU funding acknowledgment (Art. 38)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No [number].

This *[infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result]* is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No [number]

EU funding acknowledgment (Art. 38)

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank the staff of the Poultry Breeding Facilities (INRA, Unité Expérimentale Pôle Expérimental Avicole de Tours, INRA, Nouzilly, France) and of the Rearing Facilities (INRA, Unité Expérimentale Elevage Alternatif et Santé des Monogastriques, INRA, Le Magneraud, France). This study was supported by Feed-a-Gene, a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 633531.

Avoid Errors when reporting costs

- **Annex 2** is an estimate – **Sound financial management**
- **Keep records and supporting documents** (Art. 18)
 - Records are used to prove eligibility, keep records for actual costs, unit costs, flat rate costs and personnel timing/costs
- Ensure compliance with GA for personnel costs (unless working 100% in the action - **timesheets** are needed)

Costs in the different budget categories must be broken down in a relevant level of detail

(e.g. Meeting name – Location – Persons Attending – Costs covered)

Best Value

You **must demonstrate "best value"** in purchasing (Art. 10) and subcontracting (Art. 13)

- e.g. tender, three offers, market survey
 - standard practices and commercial agreements already in place are normally accepted
 - naming the supplier in the Grant Agreement DoA does not mean that you do not have to demonstrate best value
 - **You may not, under any circumstance, subcontract to another beneficiary**
-

Costs

Eligible	Ineligible
Actually incurred by beneficiaries	Identifiable taxes and duties
Incurred during and in connection with the action	Deductible VAT
Foreseen in Annex 1 and 2	Bank charges or exchange losses
Identifiable and verifiable	Provisions for possible future losses/charges
In compliance with national law	Interest owed
Reasonable, justified and financially sound	Excessive or reckless expenditure

Budget Transfers

Transfers and re-allocation	Amendment needed?
Budget from one beneficiary to another	NO
Budget from one budget category to another	NO
Addition/removal of tasks in Annex 1 Re-allocation of tasks in Annex 1	YES
Transfers between different forms of costs (actual costs, unit costs, etc.)	YES if no budget was foreseen for the 'form of cost' receiving the transfer
New subcontracts, new in-kind contributions	YES (strongly advised)

In summary

1. Transparent and regular communication
2. Evaluate and monitor your intervention logic
3. Keep records and other supporting documentation
4. Communicate your action
5. Deliver, disseminate and exploit your high quality outputs and results
6. Acknowledge EU support
- 7. Achieve significant impact!**

Register as Expert

- Evaluation of proposals
- Monitoring of projects
- Evaluation of programmes
- Design of R&I policy

Interested? Please join the database of external experts!

[Register as expert](#)

As new expert, you will be first requested to create your EU login account and register your profile.

Registered experts can update the profile via the My Expert Area after login.

Maria José Amaral

maria-jose.amaral@ec.europa.eu

@biomaram

Reference Documents

H2020 Annotated Grant Agreement

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

H2020 Online Manual - Grant Management

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management_en.htm

Guidance Amendment types & supporting documents

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-amend-types_en.pdf

Research Enquiry Service

<http://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?pg=enquiries>

Reference Documents

Making the most of your H2020 project – Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation

<https://www.iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E.pdf>

Social media guide for Horizon 2020 projects

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

Your Guide to IP in Horizon 2020

<https://www.iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/documents/EU-IPR-IP-Guide.pdf>

Reference Documents

Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

Data Management Plan template for Horizon 2020 projects

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/gm/reporting/h2020-tpl-oa-data-mgt-plan_en.docx

Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

Data Management Plan Online Tool

<https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/enquiries>

Reference Documents

Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE)

www.openaire.eu

Information on publishers' conditions

<http://sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php>

List of open access journals

<https://doaj.org>

Catalogue of Research Data Repositories

<http://www.re3data.org/>

Licensing research data

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guides/license-research-data>

IPR Helpdesk – Factsheet Publishing v. patenting

https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/Patenting_v_publishing_0.pdf

Reference Documents

Guidance to facilitate the implementation of targets to promote gender equality in research and innovation

http://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_gender_equality/KI-07-17-199-EN-N.pdf

European Charter & Code for Researchers

<https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter>

European Committee for Standardization – Food and Feed

<https://www.cen.eu/work/areas/food/Pages/default.aspx>

Benefits of linking Innovation and Standardization – Examples

<https://www.cencenelec.eu/research/tools/SuccessStories/Pages/default.aspx>

Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
About the project and results	About results only	About results
Multiple audiences Beyond the project's own community (include the media and the public)	Audiences that may use the results in their own work e.g. peers (scientific or the project's own community), industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers	Groups and entities that are making concrete use of results
Inform and reach out to society , show the benefits of research	Enable use and uptake of results	Best efforts to exploit the owned results, or to have them exploited by another legal entity
Grant Agreement art. 38.1 <i>Starts at the outset of the project</i>	Grant Agreement art. 29 <i>When results are available</i>	Grant Agreement art. 28 <i>When results are available and up to four years after project ended</i>

Involvement of Third Parties

Types of third parties	CHARACTERISTICS						
	Does work of the action	Provides resources or services	What is eligible?	Must be indicated in Annex 1	Indirect costs	Selecting the third party	Articles
Linked third party	YES	NO	Costs	YES	YES	Must be affiliated or have a legal link	Article 14
Subcontractors	YES	NO	Price	YES	NO	Best value for money, avoid conflict of interest	Article 13
Third party providing in-kind contributions	NO	YES	Costs	YES	YES	Cannot be used to circumvent the rules	Articles 11 and 12
Contractors	NO	YES	Price	NO	YES	Best value for money, avoid conflict of interest	Article 10
Financial support to third parties	Only if allowed in the call The beneficiaries' activity consists in providing financial support to the target population			YES	NO	According to the conditions in Annex 1	Article 15

Participants Guarantee Fund

- Aims at covering the financial risks during project implementation
- Intervenes
 - if a beneficiary does not reimburse any requested amount to the consortium or to the REA and
 - if the consortium accepts to continue the project at the same conditions without this beneficiary
- An equivalent amount will be transferred to the coordinator to allow for the continuation of the project.

Inform immediately the REA about possible financial risks

Audits and controls

- **Ex-ante checks:**

- Financial viability: systematic check for coordinators when requested EU funding for the action is \geq EUR 500 000)
- Certificate on the financial statements: only for final payments when total EU contribution claimed by the beneficiary on the basis of actual costs + unit costs for average personnel \geq EUR 325.000 (excluding e.g. flat rates)
- Certificate on the methodology: Optional for average personnel costs (now under unit costs)

- **Ex-post audits:**

- Audits of the Commission up to 2 years after the payment of the balance
- Extension of audit findings in case of systemic errors, irregularities, fraud or breach of obligations

Annex 14: WP5 communication plan presentation

WP.5 WIDEN THE IMPACT OF TN'S KNOWLEDGE
RESERVOIRS

Andrew@i4agri.org +44 7511 57 57 55
evia@i4agri.org from March 4th 2019
Comms@i4Agri.org – replace Marta ASAP.

Andrew Lazenby
CEO

COMPLEXITY IS SIMPLE.

IT'S NEVER SIMPLE TO KEEP THINGS SIMPLE.

SIMPLE SOLUTIONS REQUIRE THE MOST
ADVANCED THINKING.

PEOPLE LIKE SIMPLE
WE ARE DEALING WITH PEOPLE

TASKS.

- 5.1 ACTA M1-24
- 5.2 IFA M6-24
- 5.3 AU M6-24
- 5.4 GLZ M14-24
- 5.5 IFA M24

5.1

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES
WEBSITE , PRINT MEDIA, VIDEOS, MEDIA –
PRINT AND DIGITAL.
FORMAL DYNAMIC COMMUNICATIONS
PLAN
M1-24
TASK LEAD- ACTA.

#COMMUNICATION

5.2

DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION
DELIVER A FORMAL AND DYNAMIC PLAN
WHICH IDENTIFIES ACTORS AT EU
NATIONAL AND REGIONAL LEVELS AS WELL
AS THE KEY TOPICS AND MEDIUMS
M6-24
TASK LEAD- IFA.

*WE ALREADY HAVE ACCESS TO A POTENTIAL
10500 FOLLOWERS ON TWITTER!*

#COMMUNICATION

5.3

NETWORKING
PLAN REVIEW OF PROJECTS & PROCESS AT
EU, NATIONAL AND REGIONAL LEVEL
BUILD THE NETWORK – JOINT MEETINGS
POLICY BRIEF PAPER
M6-24
TASK LEAD- AU.

#COMMUNICATION

5.4

CROSS EXCHANGE TO WIDEN EXISTING
THEMATIC NETWORKS P2P AND X BORDER
15 CROSS EXCHANGE VISITS BETWEEN TN
COORDINATORS AND END USERS
150 PRACTICE ABSTRACTS
M14-24
TASK LEAD- GLZ.

#COMMUNICATION

5.5

POLICY BRIEF
WITH COOPERATION WITH SCAR SWG AKIS
TO CREATE AWARENESS ON OUTPUT TO
POLICY MAKERS GOV INSTITUTIONS
ADVISORY GROUPS DECISION GROUPS ETC
M14-24
TASK LEAD- IFA.

#COMMUNICATION

When?

Deliverable	Deliverable Name	Delivery (mths)
D5.1	Communication Activity Report	M24
D5.2	Dissemination Activity Report	M24
D5.3	Networking Activity Report	M24
D5.4	Paper Vision of SIB on High Impact KRs	M12
D5.5	Policy Brief	M24

Milestone	Milestone Name	Delivery (mths)
M5.1	Communication Plan Delivered	M3
M5.2	Dissemination Plan Delivered	M6
M5.3	Networking Plan Delivered	M6
M5.4	Cross exchange Plan Delivered	M18

START ON MONDAY. END IN MONTH 24. PEAK MONTHS 3-6-12-18-24.

THE MORE YOU TALK TO US THE MORE WE CAN DELIVER

THANK YOU : PLEASE ENSURE THE LOGO FILE ON GOOGLE DRIVE IS COMPLETE FOR YOUR ORGANIZATION TODAY.

Andrew Lazenby
CEO

Andrewl@i4agri.org +44 7511 57 57 55

Annex 15: WP2 Compile and evaluate EIP-AGRI Knowledge Reservoir (TNs) outputs presentation (1st day)

EURAKNOS

WP2. Compile and evaluate EIP-AGRI Knowledge Reservoir (TNs) outputs

WP2

PARTICIPANTS

- **5 pm:**
 - Gent University (Ugent, BE),
 - Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt (PSKW, BE),
 - Institutet l'élevage (IDELE, FR),
 - Gruenlandzentrum (GLZ, DE),
 - Aarhus University (AU, DK),
 - Association de coordination technique agricole (ACTA, FR)
- **2 pm:**
 - Royal Agricultural University (RAU, UK),
 - Athens University, (AUA, GR),
 - Leap FWG
 - Innovation for Agriculture (IFA, UK),
 - Hungarian Chambre of Agriculture (NAK, HU),
 - Agricultural Research Centre (ARC, EE)
- **0,5 pm:**
 - Eigern Vermogen....(EV-ILVO, BE)
- **0 pm:**
 - Research Institute of Agricultural Economics (AKI, HU)
 - Int. Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements – European Union Regional Group (IFOAM-EU)

TIMING

WP2

AIMS

- analyse the type of data and the ways data are produced, collected and stored in the current H2020 TNs: **Task leader USC**
- evaluate the format and design of KRs (as open sources) within current and past TN networks and related H2020 multi-actor projects and linked Ogs: **Task leader: IDELE**
- assess the dissemination and communication activities, materials and tools on their respective impact towards the end users, farmers, foresters and advisors, used by TNs; **Task leader: ACTA**
- analyse the multi-actor approach used by TNs in the short, medium and long term; **Task leader: GLZ**
- exchange and compile the experiences and know-how of the TNs with focus on the end-user groups: farmers, foresters and advisors. **Task leader: AU**

WP2

TASKS

- Data impact assessment of TNs: **Task 2.1 leader USC**
- Design of knowledge reservoirs within current and past TN: **Task 2.2 leader: IDELE**
- Dissemination, communication and information strategies: **Task 2.3 leader: ACTA**
- Multi-actor approach: **Task 2.4 leader: GLZ**
- Exchanging and compiling know-how TNs: **Task 2.5 leader: AU**

WP2

TASK 2.1 Data impact assessment of TNs: Task leader USC

Identify key TN partners (22 + approved in 2018)
responsible for

- a) Data management
- b) Knowledge communication
- c) Dissemination
- d) Multi-actor involvement

a) Data analysis

- a) Data produced
- b) Data collection
- c) Data stored

b) Mapping

- a) Knowledge and data
 - a) Sectors:
 - b) Regions
 - c) Sectors* biogeographic regions. Data will be crossed with LUCAS and FADN data

The multi-actor approach under WP2018-2020 : Key elements

WP2

TASK 2.1.1. Identify key TN partners

	Coordinator	Data management	Responsible Partner		multi-actor
			Communication	Dissemination	
HORIZONTAL TN					
AGRI-SPIN					
HNW-LINK					
SMART-AKIS					
AGRIFORVALOR					
AFINET	USC, Rosa Mosquera rrosa.mosquera.josada@usc.es	Soe KXX, Andrea Vityi	FEUGA, Ana Muñiz	ISA, Joana Amaral	INAORD, Willem van Collen
Inno4Grass					
SKIN					
ENABLING					
NEWSIE					
CROPS TN					
OK-Net-Arable					
FERTINNOVA					
WINETWORK			FEUGA, Ana Muñiz		
EUFRUIT					
CERERE					
INCREDIBLE					
PANACEA					
INNOSETA					
LIVESTOCK TN					
HENNOVATION					
EuroDairy					
4D4F					
EU Pig					
SheepNet					
OKNe Ecofeed					

WP2

TASK 2.1.2. Data TN management

THEMATIC NETWORKS	Data produced	Data Collected	Data Management		Web page
			Data Storage	Data Store	
HORIZONTAL TN					
AGRI-SPIN	IP	Scientific Team	Web, Booklets, Videos, tool kit		https://agri-spin.eu/
HNW-LINK	IP	partners	http://www.hnwlink.eu/outputs/		http://www.hnwlink.eu
SMART-AKIS			https://smart-akis.com/SFOPortal/#/		https://www.smart-akis.com/
AGRIFORVALOR					http://www.agriforvalor.eu/pages/home
AFINET	IP/OP Resources	partners/stakeholders	Knowledge Cloud linked to Openaire EU repository		http://www.eurafagroforestry.eu/afinet
Inno4Grass			https://www.inno4grass.eu/en/dissemination		http://www.inno4grass.eu/en/
SKIN			SKIN Good Practice Repository		http://www.stortfoodchain.eu/
ENABLING	IP	partners	https://www.enabling-project.com/public-deliverables/		https://www.enabling-project.com/
NEWSIE	IP	partners/stakeholders	Portal hosted by KU Leuven		http://www.newsie-academy.eu/
CROPS TN					
OK-Net-Arable			http://www.ok-net-arable.eu/index.php?search=In-the-ok		http://www.ok-net-arable.eu/
FERTINNOVA					http://www.fertinnova.com/
WINETWORK					http://www.winework.eu/
EUFRUIT					http://eufruit.eu/index.php?l=1
CERERE					http://cerere2020.eu/
INCREDIBLE					http://www.incredibleforest.net/
PANACEA					http://www.panacea-h2020.eu/
INNOSETA					http://www.innoستا.eu/
LIVESTOCK TN					
HENNOVATION					http://www.hennovation.eu/
EuroDairy					http://eurodairy.eu/
4D4F					http://4d4f.eu/content/about
EU Pig					http://www.eu4pig.eu/
SheepNet					http://www.sheepnet-network/
OKNe Ecofeed					http://ok-net-ecofeed.eu/

WP2

TASK 2.2 Design of knowledge reservoirs within current and past TN

Task leader: IDELE

LAYOUT	CONNECTIONS DESCRIPTIONS (OPENING OR INTERNATIONAL OR NATIONAL OFFICES INFORMATION)	FORMAT (1-6)	
		DATA PRESENTATION FORMAT	TYPE OF DATA PROVIDED (LOCAL SOFTWARE LINK WITH OTHER APPLICATIONS)
HOUSING TN			
ADRIAN			
AVIATION			
SMART-AGIS			
ADRIAN/AVIATION			
AVIATION			
AVIATION			
ADRIAN			
ADRIAN			
ADRIAN			
CRIPSI TN			
CRIPSI/AVIATION			
IMSTOCK TN			
IMSTOCK/AVIATION			

Task 2.2. Interviews

Partners

Evaluation of the format:

Each partner will answer the following questions for each TN:

- Attractiveness of the TN
- Easiness to find the KRs
- Easiness to upload information
- Easiness to obtain information

WP2

TASK 2.3 Dissemination, communication and information strategies

Task leader: ACTA

	DISSEMINATION				COMMUNICATION				INFORMATION			
	Strategies	Keys	Tools	Channels	Strategies	Keys	Tools	Channels	Strategies	Keys	Tools	Channels
3D PRINT		Web, Booklets, Videos		Twitter								Mass Direct Facebook.com/AgriFuture/
3D PRINTING		Web, Booklets, Videos										
SMART AGRI		Web, Booklets, Videos										
AGRI-DRONE/AR		Web, Booklets, Videos		http://www.agri-future.eu/pages/416300								
AR/VR		Web, Leaflet		http://www.3dmodeling.com/discussion								
IMMERSIVE		Web, Booklets, Reports, Videos						Poster				
TRAINING		Web, Booklets, Leaflets						Report				
NEWSLET		Booklet										
					DISCUSSION							
OK-Info-Action												
UP-TOWN												
WIKI-TOWN												
CLUBS/T												
COACH												
INNOVATION												
INNOVATION												
Euro Dairy												
IGAP												
EU-Fig												
Demofair												
Other Experiments												

Task 2.3. Interviews

Qualitative interviews will be held with the key partners involved in communication, dissemination and exploitation activities

Partners

Evaluation of the communication and dissemination:

Each partner will answer the following questions for each TN:

- Pros and Cons on designing the C & D activities
- Number and type of stakeholders reached
- Number and type of materials developed and relationship with the Number of stakeholders reached

WP2

TASK 2.4. • Multi-actor approach: Task leader: GLZ

THEMATIC NETWORKS	Types of actors					Involvement of Stakeholders			
	Farmers	Policy	Multipiers	Students	Extension services	Meeting descriptions	Stakeholders collaboration in writing materials	Stakeholders collaboration in videos	Field visits
Horizontal TN									
AGRI-SPIN									
HNW-LINK									
SMART-AXIS									
AGRIFORVALOR	?	Y			Y				N
AFINET									
Imo-Grass	Y								N
SKIN									
ENABLING									
NEWBIE									
CROPS TN									
OK-Net-Arable									
PERTINDWA									
WINETWORK									
EUFRUIT									
CERERE									
INCREDIBLE									
PANACEA									
INNOSETA									
LIVESTOCK TN									
HENNOVATION									
Euro Dairy									
404F									
EU Pig									
SheepNet									
OKne Ecofeed									

Task 2.4. Interviews

Qualitative interviews will be held with the key partners and the actors of the TNs, in particular farmers, foresters and advisors to further refine the desk top stud

Partners

Evaluation of the multiactor approach:

Each partner will answer the following questions for each TN:

- Pros and Cons on the approach taken
- Number and type of stakeholders reached
- Number and type of materials developed with the stakeholders
- Degree of involvement of stakeholders along the project

WP2

TASK 2.5 Exchanging and compiling know-how TNs

Task leader: AU

5.1 summarize the results on the current practices and methodologies of tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4.

5.2 A 2-days workshop on KR TN impact assessment will be organized
** A 2-days workshop on TN impact assessment will be organised with consortium+ + KIP + SIB to be organised in cooperation with WP5.

Thanks!

mrosa.mosquera.losada@usc.es

Annex 16: Branding workshop

Branding workshop EURAKNOS recap

leapFORWARD
design & innovation group

A brand is all that is communicated visually and otherwise to portray the personality of the organisation, it's products and services. And, as such, strong brands are enormously powerful business tools.

It's not simply a logo. An organisations logo stands as an emblem for all that their brand encompasses. It's also more than a logo. It's about the right colours, typography, tone of voice, communication channels, imagery ...

The strategic approach

- Branding is a business challenge which requires the implementation of a robust strategy
- To be successful a company's brand must fit with its products, services and the markets
- Good branding takes all the parts into consideration from the way the company behaves (brand personality) to the way it looks (the visual identity)

The visual identity

- The visual representation of the brand.
- This visual language gets represented on all marketing collateral such as sales literature, websites, signage etc.
- It will effect the way the organisation is perceived.

Agenda

- Getting to know each other
- Value exercise
- Detailed value exercises & visual exercise in groups

Getting to know each other

portugal
denmark
uk
italy
belgium
estonia
hungary
germany
spain
france
spain
greece

airplane
bike
train
car
plane
bicycle

Most used values

- Knowledge
- Simple
- Clear
- Communication
- Innovation
- Sharing
- Impact
- Networking
- Challenging

Value exercise

Futuristic

- We're doing more than in history

Timeless

- Permanent challenge because there is a lot of info
- We have the past, the existing tools and the future, we can make impact for the future

Complex

The data is complex

Complex, but the tool itself should be simple

Simple

- Info should be standard, searchable
- Can we make it simple for end users? (if children understand it it's simple enough)
- Tasks in projects are simple, the content is complex

Customer centric

Focus on future, that's focus on the end user. The user is the filter for the database. It's the user we're building the platform for.

Knowledge centric

If we're customer-central we won't be starting with the network as starting point, but with the customer and its needs.

Competitive

/

Working together

One for all, sharing info, sharing knowledge 100%

Progressive

- It should be flexible to be future proof
- Hope we present data in a progressive way

Stable

- It's not very disruptive

Risky

- Lot's of assumptions (access, build network...)
- 2 years enough? Is the quality of the data high enough?

Safe

- Top experts in the team
- It's not risky if other peoples data is bad
- As long as we learn from it is failing not a bad thing

Detailed value exercise

The Euraknos project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863

If Euraknos was a superhero

Who / what are the bad guys?

- Noise
- Linear knowledge transfer processes
- Protectionism
- Knowledge locked. Up / lack of access
- Competitors trying to build & promote a central system
- Sceptical farmers
- Walk away projects
- Hackers & bugs
- Complexity of databases
- Data: numbers
- Time
- Different views on project

Matching images

Matching images

- Collaboration
- Sustainability
- Value of money for end-users
- Simplify
- Happy farmer + other end users
- Great ideas
- Library for knowledge
- Finding the right info / solutions
- Money & sustainability for the farmer
- One platform, different sources
- Forrest: different things that work as one forrester

Images that don't match

- Driven by one type of knowledge
- Topdown approach
- Floated by information
- Academic
- Difficult to search
- Disorganised
- Quality over quantity
- Not research
- Shouldn't give work, there will be less work
- Won't make people unhappy
- No competition internally

Moodboard

Moodboard

- Green / white
- Sans-serif
- Positive
- Dynamic
- Clean

Proposal brand values

Knowledge

A lot of knowledge in the tool & in the group

Simple

It's a complex tool, but for the target audience everything will be more simple, clear & clean than it is today.

Impactful

With the tool we'll have a lot of impact on the target audience

Annex 17: WP2 Compile and evaluate EIP-AGRI Knowledge Reservoir (TNs) outputs presentation (2nd day)

WP2

PARTICIPANTS

- 5 pm:
 - Gent University (Ugent, BE),
 - Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt (PSKW, BE),
 - Institut t l'élevage (IDELE, FR),
 - Gruenlandzentrum (GLZ, DE),
 - Aarhus University (AU, DK),
 - Aassociation de coordination technique agricole (ACTA, FR)
- 2 pm:
 - Royal Agricultural University (RAU, UK),
 - Athens Univesity, (AUA, GR),
 - Biosense Institute (BIOS),
 - Innovation for Agriculture (IFA, UK),
 - Hungarian Chambre of Agriculture (NAK, HU),
 - Agricultural Research Centre (ARC, EE)
- 0,5 pm:
 - Eigern Vermogen....(EV-ILVO, BE)
- 0 pm:
 - Research Institute of Agricultural Economics (AKI, HU)
 - Int. Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements – European Union Regional Group (IFOAM-EU)

TIMING

WP2

AIMS

- analyse the type of data and the ways data are produced, collected and stored in the current H2020 TNs: **Task leader USC**
- evaluate the format and design of KRs (as open sources) within current and past TN networks and related H2020 multi-actor projects and linked Ogs: **Task leader: IDELE**
- assess the dissemination and communication activities, materials and tools on their respective impact towards the end users, farmers, foresters and advisors, used by TNs; **Task leader: ACTA**
- analyse the multi-actor approach used by TNs in the short, medium and long term; **Task leader: GLZ**
- exchange and compile the experiences and know-how of the TNs with focus on the end-user groups: farmers, foresters and advisors. **Task leader: AU**

WP2

TASKS

- Data impact assessment of TNs: **Task 2.1 leader USC**
- Design of knowledge reservoirs within current and past TN: **Task 2.2 leader: IDELE**
- Dissemination, communication and information strategies: **Task 2.3 leader: ACTA**
- Multi-actor approach: **Task 2.4 leader: GLZ**
- Exchanging and compiling know-how TNs: **Task 2.5 leader: AU**

WP2

TASK 2.1 Data impact assessment of TNs: Task leader USC

Identify key TN partners (22 + approved in 2018) responsible for

- a) Data management
 - b) Knowledge communication
 - c) Dissemination
 - d) Multi-actor involvement
- a) Data analysis
- a) Data produced
 - b) Data collection
 - c) Data stored
- b) Mapping
- a) Knowledge and data
 - a) Sectors:
 - b) Regions
 - c) Sectors* biogeographic regions. Data will be crossed with LUCAS and PADN data

WP2

TASK 2.1.1. Identify key TN partners

	Coordinator	Data management	Responsible Partner		
			Communication	Dissemination	multi-actor
HORIZONTAL TN					
AGRI-SPIN					
HNW-LINK					
SMART-AGIS					
AGRIFORVALOR					
AFINET	USC, Rosa Mosquera rrosa.mosquera@uac.es	Soe KIX, Andrea Wityl	FEUGA, Ana Muñiz	ISA, Joana Amaral	INAGRO, Willem van Collen
Inno4Grass					
SKIN					
ENABLING					
NEWSIE					
CROPS TN					
OK-Net-Arable					
FERTINNOWA					
WINETWORK			FEUGA, Ana Muñiz		
EUFruit					
CERERE					
INCREDIBLE					
PANACEA					
INNOSETA					
LIVESTOCK TN					
HENNOVATION					
EuroDairy					
404F					
EU Pig					
SheepNet					
OKNe EcoFeed					

WP2. Task 2.1.2

TASK 2.1.1. Data TN management

THEMATIC NETWORKS	Data produced	Data Collected	Data Management		Web page
			Data Storage	Data Storage	
HORIZONTAL TN					
AGRI-SPIN	24	Scientific Team	Web, Booklets, Videos, tool kit		https://agripin.eu/
HNW-LINK	18	partners	http://www.hnwlink.eu/outputs/		http://www.hnwlink.eu/
SMART-AGIS			https://smart-agis.com/FOPOportal/		https://www.smart-agis.com/
AGRIFORVALOR					https://www.agriforvalor.eu/pages/home
AFINET	24/24 Resources	partners/stakeholders	Knowledge Cloud linked to Openaire EU repository		http://www.agriforvalor.eu/afinet
Inno4Grass			https://www.inno4grass.eu/en/dissemination		http://www.inno4grass.eu/en/
SKIN			SKIN Good Practice Repository		http://www.shortfoodchain.eu/
ENABLING	24	partners	https://www.enabling-project.com/public-deliverables/		https://www.enabling-project.com/
NEWSIE	24	partners/stakeholders	Portal hosted by KU Leuven		http://www.newsie-academy.eu/
CROPS TN					
OK-Net-Arable			http://www.ok-net-arable.eu/index.php?search-in-the-ok		http://www.ok-net-arable.eu/
FERTINNOWA					http://www.fertinnowa.com/
WINETWORK					http://www.winework.eu/
EUFruit					http://eufriin.eu/index.php?id=1
CERERE					http://cerere2020.eu/
INCREDIBLE					http://www.incredibleforest.net/
PANACEA					http://www.panacea-h2020.eu/
INNOSETA					http://www.innoseta.eu/
LIVESTOCK TN					
HENNOVATION					http://www.hennovation.eu/
EuroDairy					http://eurodairy.eu/
404F					http://404f.eu/content/about
EU Pig					http://www.eu4pig.eu/
SheepNet					http://www.sheepnet.network/
OKNe EcoFeed					http://ok-net-ecofeed.eu/

Project ID	Project Name	Start Date	End Date	Status	Lead PI	Co-PIs	Partners	Impact	Dissemination
1	Project 1	2020-01-01	2022-12-31	Completed	Dr. Smith	Dr. Jones	Partner A, Partner B	High	Extensive
2	Project 2	2021-03-01	2023-06-30	In Progress	Dr. Brown	Dr. White	Partner C, Partner D	Medium	Some
3	Project 3	2022-01-01	2024-12-31	Planned	Dr. Green	Dr. Black	Partner E, Partner F	Low	None

CONTENT. Management

System Design	Management	Production and profitability
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ New AF systems design based on: ✓ Tree/crop/livestock combinations. ✓ Identification of suitable species/varieties/breeds for AF systems. ✓ Development of shade-tolerant crops and swards. ✓ Tree/crop plot distribution. ✓ Development of decision support tools/best practices. ✓ Crop diversification ✓ Crop rotation 	<p>TREE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Tree protection from wildlife and livestock. ✓ Tree mulching material. ✓ Non-timber uses of trees (fodder, chipped wood for energy, biomass, composting or livestock bedding..). <p>PEST</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Systemic pest and disease control. <p>PERMANENT GRASSLAND</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Grazing management. <p>PERMANENT CROPS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Fertilization <p>ARABLE CROPS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Irrigation ✓ Fertilization 	<p>VALUE CHAIN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Testing new combinations, e.g. integrating agriculture (crops or livestock) into plantations/orchards; making better use of tree understorey. ✓ Developing market channels and branding AF products to attract price premium. ✓ Modifying the legislation.

CONTENT. SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

Economy	Environment	Social
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Alternative economic tools ✓ Value chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Water ✓ Nutrient Cycling ✓ Mitigation ✓ Adaptation ✓ Biodiversity ✓ Circular Economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Gender ✓ Ageing ✓ Youth

CONCEPTUAL Maps Projects

4.- Greater user acceptance of collected solutions and more intensive dissemination to end-users.

CONCEPTUAL MAPS EIP-AGRI AGROFORESTRY FOCUS GROUP

Conceptual maps Operational Groups

Face to Face interviews: Qualitative interviews will be held with the key partners and actors of the TNs, in particular farmers, foresters and advisors to further refine the desk top study.

What is the aim of the interview?

Partners

Farmers and foresters

Advisors

To be jointly done for Tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4

WP2

TASK 2.2 Design of knowledge reservoirs within current and past TN

Task leader: IDELE

TASK 2.2	FORMAT (1-4)		DATA PRESENTATION FORMAT	
	CONNECTED DESCRIPTIONS (SPINULAR OR INTERACTIVE OR NATIONAL OFFICIAL ORGANISATIONS)	TYPE OF DATA RESOURCES (2-10)	SOFTWARE	LINK WITH OTHER ACTIVITIES
	RESEARCH TN			
SDG-SPIN				
IRVY-LINK				
SMART-GIS				
AGRIFORMALOR				
AFNET				
INNOV4GRI				
SDN				
ENABLING				
NEWSIE				
	COOP TN			
OK-IMP-ANON				
REPRODUCTION				
WINTWORK				
ELURUT				
CENRE				
INCREIBLE				
PUBLICSA				
INWGTLS				
	INNOVATION TN			
REINNOVATION				
FundDirty				
ADP				
ELUPR				
ShengSim				
DBN EcoFeed				

WP2

TASK 2.3 Dissemination, communication and information strategies

Task leader: ACTA

TASK 2.3	DISSEMINATION				COMMUNICATIONS				INFORMATION			
	Strategies	Ways	Tools	Channels	Strategies	Ways	Tools	Channels	Strategies	Ways	Tools	Channels
					RESEARCH TN							
SDG-SPIN	Web, Booklets, Videos	Twitter										https://www.facebook.com/AgriFormalor/
IRVY-LINK	Web, Booklets, Videos											https://www.facebook.com/AgriFormalor/
SMART-GIS	Web, Booklets, Videos											https://www.facebook.com/AgriFormalor/
AGRIFORMALOR	Web, Booklets, Videos		http://www.agriformalor.eu/pages/hiboo									https://www.facebook.com/AgriFormalor/
AFNET	Web, Leaflet		https://www.imo4gri.eu/en/4administration				Poster					https://www.facebook.com/AgriFormalor/
INNOV4GRI	Web, Booklets, Reports, Videos											https://www.facebook.com/AgriFormalor/
SDN	Web, Booklets, Reports, Videos											https://www.facebook.com/AgriFormalor/
ENABLING	Leaflets											https://www.facebook.com/AgriFormalor/
NEWSIE	booklet						Report					https://www.facebook.com/AgriFormalor/
					COOP TN							
OK-IMP-ANON												
REPRODUCTION												
WINTWORK												
ELURUT												
CENRE												
INCREIBLE												
PUBLICSA												
INWGTLS												
					INNOVATION TN							
REINNOVATION												
FundDirty												
ADP												
ELUPR												
ShengSim												
DBN EcoFeed												

WP2

TASK 2.4. • Multi-actor approach: Task leader: GLZ

THEMATIC NETWORKS	Types of actors					Involvement of Stakeholders			
	Farmers	Policy	Multipiers	Students	Extension services	Meeting descriptions	Stakeholders collaboration in writing materials	Stakeholders collaboration in videos	Field visits
Horizontal TN									
AGRI-SPIN									
HNW-LINK									
SMART-ARIS									
AGRIFORVALOR	?	Y			Y				N
AFINET									
Inno4Grass	Y								N
SKIN									
ENABLING									
NEWBIE									
CROPS TN									
OK-Net-Arable									
PORTINNOVA									
WINETWORK									
EUFRUIT									
CEREAL									
INCREDIBLE									
PANACEA									
INNOSETA									
LIVESTOCK TN									
HENNOVATION									
Euro Dairy									
4D4F									
EU Pig									
SheepNet									
OKVe Ecofeed									

WP2

TASK 2.5 Exchanging and compiling know-how TNs Task leader: AU

5.1 summarize the results on the current practices and methodologies of tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4.

5.2 A 2-days workshop on KR TN impact assessment will be organized

** A 2-days workshop on TN impact assessment will be organised with consortium+ + KIP + SIB to be organised in cooperation with WP5.

Task 2.2. Interviews

Face to Face interviews: Fostering understanding of Tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4

- Done in a common form
- Done in the own language of the Coordinator/partner, English coordinators can be interviewed by any of us
- Done by April??
- Budget for visits
- It will have quantitative short questions and qualitative questions
- Open and closed questions
- Interview content:
 - Personnel data and data project
 - Questions should consider the strategy taken and the content of the project
 - Questions should include all needed aspects of Tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4

Task 2.2. Interviews

Face to Face interviews: Qualitative interviews will be held with the key partners and actors of the TNs, in particular farmers, foresters and advisors to further refine the desk top study.

Based on the preliminary results:

What is the aim of the interview?

Partners: What they will improve, what was well accepted and what could be improved? Any barriers?

Farmers and foresters: usefulness of the material produced, easiness to include material after the project, what is missing? With a farm perspective

Advisors: usefulness of the material produced, easiness to include material after the project, what is missing? With a community perspective

Task 2.2. Interviews

Partners//Farmers//Advisors

Evaluation of the format:

Each partner will answer the following questions for each TN:

- usefulness of the TN data
- Easiness to find the KRs
- Easiness to upload information
- Easiness to obtain information

Task 2.3. Interviews

Qualitative interviews will be held with the key partners involved in communication, dissemination and exploitation activities

Partners//Farmers//Advisors

Evaluation of the communication and dissemination:

Each partner will answer the following questions for each TN:

- Pros and Cons on designing the C & D activities
- Number and type of stakeholders reached
- Number and type of materials developed and relationship with the Number of stakeholders reached

Task 2.4. Interviews

Qualitative interviews will be held with the key partners and the actors of the TNs, in particular farmers, foresters and advisors to further refine the desk top stud

Partners//Farmers//Advisors

Evaluation of the multiactor approach:

Each partner will answer the following questions for each TN:

- Pros and Cons on the approach taken
- Number and type of stakeholders reached
- Number and type of materials developed with the stakeholders
- Degree of involvement of stakeholders along the project

Open discussion done in small groups (5 people maximum)

•Interview content:

- Structure of the interview
 - Which is the best structure for the interview (15 min)
 - Discuss the main questions that you think we should have in each Task, considering:
 - T2.1 TN general questions (to partners, farmers and advisors) (15 min each)
 - T2.2. K reservoir (to partners, farmers and advisors) (15 min each)
 - T2.3 Dissemination, communication and information strategies (to partners, farmers and advisors) (15 min each)
 - T2.4 Multiactor approach (to partners, farmers and advisors) (15 min each)

Annex 18: WP3 Design a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR)

WP3 to determine the harmonised approach to design and format the next HIKR to be used in projects such as TNs and other multi-actor H2020 projects.

Statements and main ambition for EURAKNOS

Thematic Networks Know. Reservoirs	European High Impact Know. Reservoir
Focusing on sectoral issues	To boost cross-fertilisation
Combining competences to answer to farmers' and foresters' requests	Building the capacity of knowledge intermediaries and knowledge brokers to identifying, assessing, and repackaging knowledge for a range of audiences
Risk of « walk alone » of certain KR	To ensure sustainability of these knowledge networks and maximise their outputs for end-users

From the diversity of sites....

Best practices

Knowledge Reservoirs
Or
Farmer support tool

From the diversity of contents

TN/Disseminati on material	Nb Mat	AFINET	FERTIN NOWA	Smart - AKIS	Sheep Net	Hennovati on	OK- Net Arable	4D4F	WINE- NETWORK	INNO-GRASS
Website	Nr	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2 (web +KR)	1
	Imp	+++	++	+++	++	++	+	?	+++	+++
You tube	Nr	10	12	N/A	11	4	16	30	157 vidéos	104
	Imp	++	--	N/A	?	+++	+++	?	++ (562 views)	++
EIP-AGRI Practice abstracts	Nr	20	104	55	0	38	50	100	60	100
	Imp	Pending	?	?				+++	+	?
Newsletter	Nr	6	6	5				?	4: in 7 language	Not defined
	Imp	++	+++	++				+++	+++	++
Fact sheets	Nr	40	25	N/A				36 (12 bests practices)	24 leaflets	48
	Imp	+++	?	N/A				++	++	+++
Press releases and articles	Nr	40	46	68				100	163	10
	Imp	++	+++	?				+	+++	+++
Scientific papers	Nr	10	5	6				0	3	10
	Imp	Pending	?	++				N/A	++	++
Technology review documents	Nr		136	1300 (tech cards)				240 tools	12 pp in 7 languages	5 grasslansup décisions systems
	Imp		?	+++				N/A	++	?
Technology database	Nr		250 entries	Smart AKIS platform				1 farm knowlplatform	531 docs in KR	stakeholder database
	Imp		+++	?				++	++	?
Reports exchanged technologies	Nr	3	25	0				0	5 cross exchange	25
	Imp	N/A	?	N/A	N/A	N/A	?	N/A	+++	?
Other	Nr	3 Social média	1 Farming bible	N/A	0	0	1 Social média	N/A	1 radio	Encyclopédia pratensis/1 IIMS
	Imp	**	?	N/A	N/A	N/A	+	N/A	+	++

The Euraknos project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863"

To ... an High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR)

The WP 3 to co-design an High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR)

Aims:

- define type of data (technological information, economic information, practical issues and end-users comments..)

And their management : collection, storage, quality analysis, sharing...

- define the HIKR architecture (from back to front office, ways and steps to move in and find..., internal and external links, rights and profils)

- provide technical guidelines to set up a long term sustainable HIKR in relationship with EIP-AGRI platform and provide recommendations to strengthen the multi-actor approach

Risks to face ...

The customer demand	Core skills	Informatic skills	Marketing skills	Maintenance
How the customer explained his need	How the project leader understood it	How the programmer wrote it	How the sales distributor described it	How the project was documented
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customer segments Personae Need to ensure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The value proposition newness, performance, customization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Database management Digital language and supports Digital technics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product quality Distribution channel Promotional strategy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customer assistance Hot line Back office maintenance

7

Description of work

Task 3.1: HIKR data best practices and methodologies (M8-M14)
Involved partners: LFG, AU, ARC, USC, PSKW, NAK, GLZ, RAU, UGent

Lead: IDELE

Define the best methodologies and practices to collect, generate and store knowledge data outputs of TNs.
 ⇒ **BACK OFFICE architecture and management**

(Decision tree, framework and specific recommendations for technical guidelines) for valorization of the needed information

By: **Data Work Group (WG) (meetings)**

Deliverable => D3.1 Report on HIKR methodologies and practices for data generation, selection, collection and storage (M16).

Task 3.2 Design of a HIKR (M8-M14)

Lead: Leap Forward

Involved partners: IDELE, PSKW, ARC, NAK, RAU, UGent, AU

To design the common format and tools (software, data formats) to be used for a HIKR adapted for advisory services and for end users, farmers and foresters.

⇒ FRONT OFFICE architecture and management

By : Design WG meeting (ca. 10)

Deliverable => D3.2 Report on HIKR design (M16): specifications for the HIKR software design in accordance to advisors and end users expectations and uses.

Task 3.3: HIKR dissemination recommendations (M8-M14)

Lead: RAU

Involved partners: PSKW, IDELE, ACTA, LFG, USC, NAK, GLZ, RAU, IfA, Ugent

To select the main tools to disseminate, communicate and inform end-users within the HIKR but also through EIP-AGRI and TN platforms.

Provide recommendations for common formats for practice abstracts (taking into account the type of knowledge, the means of communication, the target audiences...).

By : Info WG to identify and file recommendations

Deliverable => D3.3 Report on HIKR strategies to disseminate and communicate to the end-user and exploit innovative knowledge and data (M16).

Task 3.4: HIKR Multi-actor approach (M8-M14)

Lead: GLZ

Involved partners: PSKW, IDELE, ARC, LFG, USC, NAK , LF, AU, IfA, UGent, ACTA, RAU

To select the main tools to involve multi-actors in TNs with focus on the end user in the different phases of the project: conceptualisation, initiation, execution and post execution of the project.

To define the best practices and methods to foster the multi-actor approach for the production of knowledge (team building, training, tools and stakeholders' engagement).

By : Actor WG (ca. 10) to set up to identify and file recommendations for best methodologies and practices will be selected from the KIP.

Deliverable => D3.4 Report on HIKR multi actor approach (M16).

Report describing methodology and practices to involve multi actors in TNs .

Question ?

**How to organise Work Groups ?
(include in the WP2 observation)**

	Data	Design	Inform.	MA App.
Researchers	+	?	?	+
Farmers Foresters	?	+	+	+
Advisors	+	+	?	+
NGOs	?	+	?	+
Policy makers	?	+	?	+
Farmers assoc.	?	?	+	+
TNs & Gos	+	+	+	+
Rural Networks	+	+	+	+

Recommendations ?

- A variety of stakeholders (Knowledges, Expertises, Means...) ?
- A variety of MA approaches (stage in the process...) ?
- A variety in the objectives ? (Targets...)

Annex 19: WP4 Explore an e-Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP)

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs
Towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

WP4 - Explore an e-Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP)

Spyros Fountas – Agricultural University of Athens

EURAKNOS kick-off meeting
Friday 11 January, 2019
Ellipsgebouw, Brussels

WP4 context

WP4 aims to:

- **explore** the feasibility and added value of developing a new standardised e-KRP based on end-user needs;
- **connect** the information of selected Thematic Networks (TNs) with the uniform format decided in WP3;
- **create** a future vision for the e-KRP, in terms of UI, UX, functionality and sustainable exploitation;

Work Package Title
Explore an e-Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP)

Start Month: **6** End Month: **24**

Lead Beneficiary: **AUA**
AKI / LFG main contributors

List of Deliverables

D4.1 Report on added value and feasibility of e-KRP [M12]
D4.2 API documentation [M14]
D4.3 EURAKNOS e-KRP documentation and guide [M24]
D4.4 EURAKNOS visuals and specifications [M24]

WP4 tasks

Task 4.1 (M6 - M12; Lead: IFOAM EU)
Feasibility & added value of an e-KRP

Task 4.2 (M14 - M20; Lead: AUA)
Design & development of a prototype e-KRP

Task 4.3 (M6 - M24; Lead: LFG)
Conceptualization of the future vision for the e-KRP

2

Overview of WP4-related tasks and activities

3

Task 4.1 Feasibility and added value of an e-Knowledge Repository Platform (e-KRP)

Context and task-related activities

Context

- Systematic investigation of the feasibility and added value of developing an e-KRP based on end-user needs.
- Investigation of similar initiatives at the national and international levels (open source DBs related to agriculture & forestry).

Activities

- **Desktop study:** In depth study on the format of the presentation of data and knowledge in existing KRAs.
- **Consultations with:**
 - individual end-users,
 - end-user representatives (advisors, innovation brokers, trainers, educators, etc.), and
 - representative organisations (vocational schools, chambers of agriculture, OECD, FAO, EFSA, ...) in frame of the added value of an e-KRP.

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Task 4.2

Design and development of a prototype e-Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP)

Context and task-related activities

M14-M20
Lead: AUA
AKI / LFG main contributors

Context

- Design and development of e-KRP prototype based on outputs of WP2 and WP3.
- The e-KRP data repository will integrate the KRAs of existing Thematic Networks (TNs).
- Characteristics of the e-KRP prototype repository:
 - upgradable, and
 - scalable
 so as to meet future demands.

Activities

- **Data collection**
 - Design and development of an automated data retrieval application (**web crawler**) for "communication" with existing TNs projects and query for data and information.
- **Construction, testing and validation** of the e-KRP prototype
 - use of the EIP-AGRI platform
- Data from 8 TNs will be initially imported in the e-KRP repository.

7

e-KRP design and development lifecycle

8

Design of e-KRP on the basis of a three-tier architecture

- **Data layer (AUA, AKI)**
 - Back-end layer of a system's architecture.
 - Relates to data storage and contains a data store system.
 - Hosts the **e-KRP data repository**.
- **Application layer (AUA, AKI)**
 - Layer of the overall system's architecture relating to data processing.
 - Hosts the **search engine** that will be used for **retrieval of data** from the **e-KRP data repository**.
- **Presentation layer (LFG)**
 - Front-end layer of the system's architecture.
 - Provides a GUI to the system's end user.
 - Hosts the **e-KRP web-based application**.

Image source: <https://www.internet.com/resources/3d-defined/3-tier-architecture-compare-overview/>

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e-KRP three-tier architecture

10

Integrating data into the e-KRP data repository

e-KRP data repository the case of the MongoDB NoSQL data store

MongoDB

- is an **open-source, non-relational** data store developed in **C++**,
- stores data as **collections of JSON documents** and more specifically a binary representation of JSON called **BSON (MongoDB data model)**,
- enables handling of **highly diverse data types**,
- allows for **dynamic changes** in database schema,
- documents **map naturally** to object-oriented programming languages
- enables **faster application development**.

source: <https://www.mongodb.com/compar/mongodb-mysql>

MongoDB data model vs relational data model

relational data model

- **Data structure** is based on **tables** by making use of a **row and columnar** format.
- Data is **highly structured**.
- Structure of stored data (i.e. **database schema**) needs to be **defined in advance**.
- Requirement changes impose **migration to a new database schema**.
- **Data access** through use of **SQL queries**.

VS.

MongoDB data model

- MongoDB structures data into **collections of JSON documents**.
- A **JSON document** is made up of a set of **fields** (i.e. **key-value pairs**).
- **No need to predefine** database schema.
- Each **JSON document** has its own **schema built into its own design**.
- Data is accessed through **application code**.

source: <https://www.mongodb.com/compar/mongodb-mysql>

Input to e-KRP data repository

- A **wide range of outputs** has been produced, including:

- databases,
- IT applications,
- decision making tools, and
- dissemination material, such as:
 - videos,
 - databases,
 - abstract sheets,
 - flyers,
 - newsletters,
 - practice abstracts,
 - publications.

- Produced outputs have been made available through projects websites using **different standards, tools, IT systems or communication and dissemination channels.**

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Building a search engine on top of the e-KRP repository

Elasticsearch

- Open source, full-text search engine based on the Lucene library and developed in Java.
- Elasticsearch official clients available in Java, .NET (C#), PHP, Python, Apache Groovy, Ruby, etc.
- Can be used to search **all kinds of documents.**

source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Elasticsearch>

MongoDB faceted search

- Faceted search is a way of searching for items by **applying filters** on various properties (facets) of the collection items.
- **Important part of the UI** for many search platforms.
- MongoDB provides **built-in solution** for faceted search implementation.

source: <https://www.mongodb.com/blog/post/faceted-search-with-mongodb>

Apache Solr

- Open search platform written in Java.
- Main features: full-text search, faceted search, real-time indexing, NoSQL features, and rich document handling.
- Potential to be used for analytics use cases
- Active development community and regular releases.

source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Apache_Solr

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Task 4.3

Conceptualization of the future vision for the e-KRP

Context and task-related activities

Context

- Create a **future vision** for the e-KRP.
- Provide **meaningful insights** into **UI** and **UX** of the e_KRP by capitalizing on work conducted in WPs 2 and 3 and Tasks 4.1 & 4.2.
- Moving from e-KRP prototype **production**.
- Close **collaboration** with with TN coordinators.

M6-M24
Lead: LFG

Activities

- Implementation of appropriately designed **user-tests**.
- Data gathering from interviews with end-users after having interacted with the e-KRP prototype.
- Creation of **visuals** and **specifications** to define the future vision for the e-KRP.

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Web-based applications examples

AGRIFORVALOR
platform

18

Web-based applications examples

WINETWORK
platform

19

Web-based applications examples

WINETWORK platform

20

Web-based applications examples

4D4F Data Driven Dairy Decisions for Farmers platform

21

Web-based applications examples

OK-NET Arable platform

22

Web-based applications examples

OK-NET Arable platform

The screenshot shows a search interface with a search bar and a list of results. The results are organized into a table with columns for 'Title', 'Rating by user', and 'Date'. The results include various agricultural topics such as 'Crop rotation', 'Soil fertility', and 'Pesticide resistance'.

Nitrogen supply for winter oilseed rape

The screenshot shows a detailed application page for 'Nitrogen supply for winter oilseed rape'. It includes a title, a description, and a 'Learn more' button. The page is designed to provide specific information and resources related to nitrogen management for winter oilseed rape.

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Web-based applications examples

SMART-AKIS platform

The screenshot shows the SMART-AKIS platform interface. It features a search bar on the left and a grid of technology cards on the right. The cards include titles like 'ICT tool for improving site-specific land management', 'Economic analysis for smart sprayer applications in cold blueberry fields', and 'Leaf Chlorophyll Content & Biomass of Winter Wheat'. Each card has a small image and a 'Learn more' button.

SMART-AKIS platform

This screenshot shows another part of the SMART-AKIS platform, displaying a different set of technology cards. The cards are arranged in a grid and include titles such as 'Leaf Chlorophyll Content & Biomass of Winter Wheat' and 'Economic analysis for smart sprayer applications in cold blueberry fields'. Each card has a small image and a 'Learn more' button.

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Web-based applications examples

SMART-AKIS platform

The screenshot shows the SmartRain App interface. It features a large thermometer graphic on the left, a central image of a smartphone displaying the app, and a list of benefits on the right. The benefits include 'Productivity (crop yield per ha)', 'Revenue, profit, farm income', 'Quality of product', and 'Sell livestock'. Each benefit has a small icon and a 'Learn more' button.

SMART-AKIS platform

This screenshot shows another part of the SMART-AKIS platform, displaying the SmartRain App interface. It features a large thermometer graphic on the left, a central image of a smartphone displaying the app, and a list of benefits on the right. The benefits include 'Productivity (crop yield per ha)', 'Revenue, profit, farm income', 'Quality of product', and 'Sell livestock'. Each benefit has a small icon and a 'Learn more' button.

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Thank you for your attention!

